

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.9	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	18
C05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	20
C06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	236	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	4720
E06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	240	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	4800
F05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	262	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	5240
F06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	230	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	4600
G05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	16
G06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	254	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	5080
H05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
H06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.9	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	18
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.76	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	15.2
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	80.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	1616
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	85.6	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	1712
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	22
F07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	20

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				0	15978						15978
				0	15511						15511
				0	13243						13243
		1.5	0.5	12	15821						15833
		1.6	0.5	12	14497						14509
				0	16878						16878
				0	14682						14682
				0	17222						17222
		245	228	2866	12884						15750
		248	231	3020	13362						16382
		271	253	3128	12558						15686
		238	221	2924	13555						16479
		1.4	0.4	10	14799						14809
		263	245	3095	12860						15955
				0	14996						14996
				3294	12962						16256
		1.5	0.5	11	14440						14451
		1.34	0.38	10	15427						15437
		85.6	76	1078	15168						16246
		90.5	80.9	1226	16235						17461
		1.8	0.7	16	16755						16771
		1.6	0.6	14	16208						16222

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	0	0	2146.5
	1	1	0	0	3017.3
	1	1	0	0	1444.8
	1	1	3449	3943.5	3007.4
	1	1	3958	5818	3460.6
	1	1	0	0	3069.8
	1	1	0	0	3259.1
	1	1	0	0	3022.6
	1	1	6320	20000	3135
	1	1	5875	19425	2897
	1	1	6442	19936	3144
	1	1	5552	19711	2860.8
	1	1	3485	4436.3	3070.3
	1	1	5969	19866	2891.5
	1	1	0	0	2999.2
	1	1	5942	19792	2854.8
	1	1	4930	18587	2792.3
	1	1	4507	18466	2748
	1	1	4501	19631	2742.6
	1	1	5525	19803	2711.5
	1	1	3230	11675	2705.6
	1	1	3127	10035	2713.4

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68	TotalCNVMax68
2146.5							
3017.3							
1444.8							
3008.1					1.18	0.66	
3462.5					1.28	0.72	
3069.8							
3259.1							
3022.6							
6204					240.7	231.9	
5943.9					244.1	235.4	
6492.6					266.4	257	
5850.6					234.1	225.6	
3071.2					1.07	0.57	
6184.3					258.3	249.1	
2999.2							
6286.8							
2804.3					1.19	0.65	
2758.2					1.03	0.55	
3863.3					83.2	78.3	
3911.5					88.1	83.2	
2714.1					1.43	0.87	
2719.7					1.31	0.77	

